

A Resilient Method for Smart Power Grid Synchronization Estimation Against Partial Missing Measurements

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Abstract—With the increasing demand for power system stability and resilience, effective real-time tracking plays a crucial role in smart grid synchronization. However, most studies have focused on measurement noise, while they seldom think about the problem of measurement data loss in smart power grid synchronization. To solve this problem, a resilient fault-tolerant extended Kalman filter (RFTEKF) is proposed to dynamically track voltage amplitude, voltage phase angle and frequency. First, the positive sequence fast estimation model of three-phase unbalanced network is established. Secondly, the loss phenomenon of measurements occurs in a random way and the randomness of data loss is defined by the discrete distribution of the interval $[0,1]$. Subsequently, a resilient fault-tolerant extended Kalman filter based on the real-time estimation framework is designed by using time-stamp technique to acquire partial data loss information. Finally, extensive simulation results manifest that the proposed RFTEKF can synchronize the smart grid significantly more effectively than the traditional extended Kalman filter (EKF).

Index Terms—Power systems, synchronized measurements, dynamic state estimation, Kalman filter, partial missing measurements, smart grid.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, great changes have taken place in the power grid [1-2]. On the one hand, there has been an increase in the rate of renewable energy generation

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integration.; on the other hand, intelligent load control, energy storages and new energy vehicles are also widely deployed [3]. This evolution will provide stochastic operating behavior and enhance the power grid's dynamic properties. At the same time, so that issues like the rising demand for electricity and the greenhouse effect can be adequately addressed, the public policy goals have been developed by various governments. For instance, in the development of new energy installed capacity, by 2030, China's total installed power capacity will increase to 3.8 billion kilowatts, and the proportion of clean energy installed capacity will reach 68%. It is not hard to predict that the deployment of distributed generation systems (DPGS) will increase at a high rate of speed due to the need to produce more clean energy [4]. As a key factor in the accurate control of grid-connected converters and DPGS, the grid synchronization with high accuracy is necessary and vital. Without precise grid synchronization, the network of our utility many face the issue of instability or even black-out [5-6].

To date, a variety of power grid synchronization methods have been proposed in the literature [7]. In general, these prior-art synchronization approaches can be broken down into the following groups:

a) The first category is mathematical analysis approaches, which are mainly based on the digital signal processing (DSP) techniques, which have strict requirements on the sampling rate [8].

b) The zero crossing technique is easier to realize and create; however, it is susceptible to the voltage alterations of power grid, especially for the harmonics and notches. Therefore, the reliability of the approach needs to be improved to meet the practical application [9].

c) Based on Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) technology, for balanced three-phase voltages, several approaches that can detect the precise phase and frequency [10-13]. However, these methods face a potential instability issue in the converter and generator that maybe resulted from various reasons, such as PLL time delay, large harmonics, inaccurate modeling parameters, severe unbalanced voltages to cite a few.

Except the methods mentioned above, recent advances in state estimation (SE) methods [14], which were first suggested in [15] and [16], are a key component of the grid synchronization technology. More importantly, recent advances in computing and phasor techniques have made it

possible to use high-speed time-synchronization data captured by PMUs to do real-time dynamic estimate. The majority of the publications that were published concentrated on the effect of measurement noise on the grid synchronization estimation accuracy. Since the distribution of measurement noise is usually unknown and often deviates from the assumed Gaussian model, resulting in outliers, a robust estimation framework is designed in [17] to solve the unknown non-Gaussian noise and measurement time bias problems and obtain the optimal estimation. In reference [18], a CKF method based on generalized entropy loss (GCL) is proposed for complex non-Gaussian noise in power systems, so as to improve the accuracy and flexibility of dynamic state estimation when there is bad measurement information. In reference [19], the concept of adaptive state estimation of power system measured by PMU is proposed in view of the uncertainty and time-variability of measurement error characteristics. A Gaussian Laplacian mixed model is established to fit the unknown measurement error, and an adaptive estimation framework is proposed to generate more accurate state estimation.

However seldom with regard to the impact of measurement data partial loss [20-21]. As a result of sensor data dropouts in transmission channels of conventional measurements from meters to the control center, the missing data phenomenon constitutes one of the major concerns in estimating power grid synchronization [22-24]. As noted in [25], the measurement signal from the sensor may include the damaged signal result from the potential sensor malfunction, which is not always correct. The sensor data loss may degrade the performance of conventional dynamic state estimator, which can severely distort the estimation results, result in completely unreliable state estimates [26-28].

To deal with the issue of missing measurements, some significant studies have been conducted in [29-30]. Most existing literature models missing measurements as a random variable that obeys the Bernoulli distribution, with sensor data assumed to be either utterly missing or completely available. The phenomenon of partial measurement missing, however, is relatively common as well in practical applications, as it is rare for complete measurements to be lost [25]. As an example, PMU data are converted from continuous measurement signals to digital data using analog to digital converters (ADCs). Poorly designed peripheral circuits or an unstable reference voltage can lead to fading output from ADCs [31]. It is important to keep in mind that the problem of partially missing measurements is very different from the problem of lost measurement data, which was covered in the earlier study [32], which should be re-evaluated. *To the best of authors' knowledge, the power grid synchronization with partial missing measurements has not been fully investigated. This also constitutes the main motivation of our current research.*

The purpose of this paper is to develop a novel resilient fault tolerant extended Kalman filter (RFTEKF), which can provide more reliable dynamic state estimation in power grid synchronization when partial measurements are missing.

Comparatively to conventional EKFs, it can track power grid synchronization information more effectively. The main contributions of this paper are highlighted as follows:

Fig. 1. Diagram of the proposed RFTEKF method.

- The estimation model of smart grid synchronization with partial measurement missing is established, where the time stamp technology is utilized to acquire the sensor data loss information.
- A novel resilient fault tolerant extended Kalman filter is proposed and derived, in which the gain is calculated using only the statistical characteristic of the lost information, where the randomness of partial missing is represented by a discrete distribution in the interval of [0,1].
- Extensive simulation results show that the efficiency of the proposed method and demonstrate that RFTEKF can provide more accurate results than the conventional EKF and FTEKF.

Following is the remainder of this paper. First, the state space model for the smart grid synchronization with partial measurement missing is established in Section II. Then, Section III infers the conventional extended Kalman filter and the proposed resilient fault tolerant extended Kalman filter approach with specificity. Subsequently, to assess the effectiveness of the suggested approach, extensive simulations are performed on various test systems and the estimation results are then provided, and finally the conclusions are presented in Section V.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Basic Theory

In general, the general form of three-phase power system voltages can be expressed by

$$\begin{cases} v_a(t) = \sqrt{2}V_a \cos(\omega t + \phi_a) \\ v_b(t) = \sqrt{2}V_b \cos(\omega t + \phi_b) \\ v_c(t) = \sqrt{2}V_c \cos(\omega t + \phi_c) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $v_a(t), v_b(t), v_c(t)$ are the instantaneous unbalanced voltage of a, b, c phases, respectively; t represents the time in seconds; ω indicates the electrical angular frequency in rad/s . $V_i (i = a, b, c)$ is the RMS voltage amplitudes, and

ϕ_i is the corresponding RMS phase angles. Note that, the voltage magnitudes of each phase are not equal necessarily, and the phase different between each phase voltage might not be 120° .

From equation (1), the discrete three-phase voltages can be derived as

$$\begin{cases} v_a(k) = \sqrt{2}V_a \cos(\omega kT + \phi_a) \\ v_b(k) = \sqrt{2}V_b \cos(\omega kT + \phi_b) \\ v_c(k) = \sqrt{2}V_c \cos(\omega kT + \phi_c) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $k=0,1,2,3,\dots$ represents the sampling instant. T is sampling period, $x(k) = x(kT)$ corresponds to the magnitude of $x(t)$ at the k th time instant. In general, the frequency of power grid is considered to be 60 Hz, and the sampling frequency is 2400 Hz.

The variable $v(k) = [v_a(k), v_b(k), v_c(k)]^T$ represents the three-phase voltage vector. According to the symmetrical component transformation, the unbalanced three-phase voltage can be represented as

$$v(k) = v_0(k) + v_p(k) + v_n(k) \quad (3)$$

where $v(k)$ is the instantaneous three-phase voltage at time instant k ; $v_p(k)$, $v_n(k)$ represent the positive, negative sequence voltages, respectively; $v_0(k)$ represents the zero sequence voltage

$$\begin{cases} v_p(k) = \sqrt{2}V_p [\cos(\theta_p), \cos(\theta_p - 120^\circ), \cos(\theta_p + 120^\circ)]^T \\ v_n(k) = \sqrt{2}V_n [\cos(\theta_n), \cos(\theta_n + 120^\circ), \cos(\theta_n - 120^\circ)]^T \\ v_0(k) = \sqrt{2}V_0 [\cos(\theta_0), \cos(\theta_0), \cos(\theta_0)]^T \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\theta_p, \theta_n, \theta_0$ are respectively represent the positive, negative and zero sequence phase angles.

According to the symmetric component transformation, the three-phase voltage phasors under the abc coordinate frame can be separated into the zero, positive, and negative sequence phasors

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_a \\ \bar{V}_b \\ \bar{V}_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & a^2 & a \\ 1 & a & a^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_0 \\ \bar{V}_p \\ \bar{V}_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $a = 1 \angle 120^\circ$.

In addition, by using the Clarke's transformation, the abc coordinate frame voltages phasors can be transformed into the voltage phasors of stationary $\alpha\beta$ coordinate frame

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_\alpha \\ \bar{V}_\beta \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_a \\ \bar{V}_b \\ \bar{V}_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

By combining (5) and (6), the following can be derived

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_\alpha \\ \bar{V}_\beta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -j & j \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_p \\ \bar{V}_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Furthermore, the voltages phasors \bar{V}_α and \bar{V}_β can be discretized as $v_\alpha(k)$ and $v_\beta(k)$

$$\begin{aligned} v_\alpha(k) &= \sqrt{2}V_p \cos(\omega kT + \phi_p) + \sqrt{2}V_n \cos(\omega kT + \phi_n) \\ &= \sqrt{2}(V_p \cos \phi_p + V_n \cos \phi_n) \cos \omega kT - \\ &\quad \sqrt{2}(V_p \sin \phi_p + V_n \sin \phi_n) \sin \omega kT \\ &= \sqrt{2}V_\alpha \cos(\omega kT + \phi_\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v_\beta(k) &= \sqrt{2}V_p \sin(\omega kT + \phi_p) - \sqrt{2}V_n \sin(\omega kT + \phi_n) \\ &= \sqrt{2}(V_p \cos \phi_p - V_n \cos \phi_n) \sin \omega kT + \\ &\quad \sqrt{2}(V_p \sin \phi_p - V_n \sin \phi_n) \cos \omega kT \\ &= \sqrt{2}V_\alpha \cos(\omega kT + \phi_\beta) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Note that after using the Clarke's transformation, the zero sequence quantities in (7) are zeros.

B. Smart Grid Synchronization System Model

According to Eqs. (8)-(9), the discrete grid synchronous voltage state space variables with sampling period T are chosen as follows

$$\begin{cases} x_1(k) = \sqrt{2}V_\alpha \cos(k\omega T + \phi_\alpha) \\ x_2(k) = \sqrt{2}V_\alpha \sin(k\omega T + \phi_\alpha) \\ x_3(k) = \sqrt{2}V_\beta \cos(k\omega T + \phi_\beta) \\ x_4(k) = \sqrt{2}V_\beta \sin(k\omega T + \phi_\beta) \\ x_5(k) = \omega T \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $t = kT$ and $T = 1/f_s$, T and f_s are the sampling time and frequency, respectively.

According to (10), the smart grid synchronization system model can be formulated as follows

$$\begin{cases} x_1(k+1) = x_1(k) \cos(x_5(k)) - x_2(k) \sin(x_5(k)) \\ x_2(k+1) = x_1(k) \sin(x_5(k)) + x_2(k) \cos(x_5(k)) \\ x_3(k+1) = x_3(k) \cos(x_5(k)) - x_4(k) \sin(x_5(k)) \\ x_4(k+1) = x_3(k) \sin(x_5(k)) + x_4(k) \cos(x_5(k)) \\ x_5(k+1) = x_5(k) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The process noise in (11) is usually considered to be zero. The measurement functions are expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} z_1(k) &= x_1(k) + \zeta_1(k) \\ z_2(k) &= x_3(k) + \zeta_2(k) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\zeta_1(k)$ and $\zeta_2(k)$ are deemed to be external disturbances.

C. Calculation of The Positive Sequence Voltage

At first, by taking invert the matrix in (7), the following equation can be derived

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_p \\ \bar{V}_n \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & j \\ 1 & -j \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_\alpha \\ \bar{V}_\beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Then, based on the Euler's formula, the positive voltage vector can be derived by expanding the first row of the matrix (13)

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{V}_p &= V_p \angle \theta_p = \frac{1}{2} (\bar{V}_\alpha + j\bar{V}_\beta) \\ &= 0.5[(V_\alpha \cos \theta_\alpha - V_\beta \sin \theta_\beta) + j(V_\alpha \sin \theta_\alpha + V_\beta \cos \theta_\beta)] \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Thus, the magnitude and phase angle of positive sequence voltage can be acquired as follows [32]

$$\theta_p = \tan^{-1} \frac{V_\alpha \sin(\theta_\alpha) + V_\beta \cos(\theta_\beta)}{V_\alpha \cos(\theta_\alpha) - V_\beta \sin(\theta_\beta)} \quad (15)$$

$$V_p = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{(V_\alpha \sin \theta_\alpha + V_\beta \cos \theta_\beta)^2 + (V_\alpha \cos \theta_\alpha - V_\beta \sin \theta_\beta)^2} \quad (16)$$

D. Smart Grid Synchronization System Model with Partial Missing Measurements

Based on the smart grid synchronization system model described by Eqs. (11)-(12), the discrete power grid system process and measurement equations with partial missing measurements can be expressed by

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k) + \mathbf{v}_k \\ \mathbf{y}_k = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_k^1 \Gamma^1(\mathbf{x}_k) + \boldsymbol{\zeta}_k^1 \\ \gamma_k^2 \Gamma^2(\mathbf{x}_k) + \boldsymbol{\zeta}_k^2 \\ \vdots \\ \gamma_k^m \Gamma^m(\mathbf{x}_k) + \boldsymbol{\zeta}_k^m \end{pmatrix} = \boldsymbol{\Xi}_k \Gamma(\mathbf{x}_k) + \boldsymbol{\zeta}_k \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where

$\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbf{R}^n$ -state variable;

$\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbf{R}^m$ -measurement vector with partial measurements missing;

$\mathbf{f}, \boldsymbol{\Gamma}$ -system and measurement functions;

$\mathbf{v}_k, \boldsymbol{\zeta}_k$ -process noise and measurement noise, which are commonly depicted as zero-mean Gaussian white noises with covariance matrices \mathbf{Q}_k and \mathbf{R}_k , respectively.

In addition, $\boldsymbol{\Xi}_k = \text{diag}\{\gamma_k^1, \gamma_k^2, \dots, \gamma_k^m\}$ and $\gamma_k^i (i=1, 2, \dots, m)$ are m independent random variables, which are independent of the system noise and measurement noise. Where $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \text{diag}\{\Gamma^1(\mathbf{x}_k), \Gamma^2(\mathbf{x}_k), \dots, \Gamma^m(\mathbf{x}_k)\}$, and the random variable $\gamma_{m,k}$ represents the m th measurement partial loss coefficient, which obeys the uniform distribution of $[0, 1]$ interval.

III. PROPOSED RESILIENT FAULT TOLERANT EXTENDED KALMAN FILTER

In this section, as an important theoretical basis, the main implementation framework of conventional extended Kalman filter method is introduced briefly at first. Then, to acquire a more reliable dynamic state estimation that can deal with the issue of partial missing measurements in the PMU-based

power grid synchronization, a novel resilient fault tolerant extended Kalman filter is developed and proved.

To facilitate the derivation of resilient fault tolerant extended Kalman filter approach, some basic theories and necessary lemmas will be introduced in advance.

Lemma 1[33]: Given two matrices $\mathbf{A}_{m \times n}$ and $\mathbf{B}_{n \times n}$, where $\mathbf{B}_{n \times n} = \mathbf{B}_{n \times n}^T$, then the partial derivative of $\text{tr}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^T)$ with respect to \mathbf{A} can be derived as follows

$$\frac{\partial \text{tr}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^T)}{\partial \mathbf{A}} = 2\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} \quad (18)$$

where $\text{tr}(\cdot)$ represents the trace of matrix.

Lemma 2[34]: Given a real-valued matrix $\mathbf{A} = [a_{ij}]_{p \times p}$ and a diagonal stochastic matrix $\mathbf{B} = \text{diag}(b_1, b_2, \dots, b_p)$, then

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}^T) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}(b_1^2)\mathbf{E}(b_1 b_2) \cdots \mathbf{E}(b_1 b_p) \\ \mathbf{E}(b_1 b_2)\mathbf{E}(b_2^2) \cdots \mathbf{E}(b_2 b_p) \\ \cdots \\ \mathbf{E}(b_p b_1)\mathbf{E}(b_p b_2) \cdots \mathbf{E}(b_p^2) \end{bmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{A} \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{E}(\cdot)$ is the mathematical expectation, \otimes represents the Hadamard product.

For the sake of convenience, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-$ denotes the prior estimator of \mathbf{x}_k , $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+$ represents the posteriori estimate of \mathbf{x}_k , which are expressed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^- = \mathbf{E}[\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{k-1}] \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+ = \mathbf{E}[\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_k] \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

A. Extended Kalman Filter

As a conventional nonlinear dynamic state estimator, EKF has been widely used in state estimation and parameter identification of nonlinear system [35-36].

In general, the recursive form of EKF can be summarized as follows

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^- = \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+) \quad (21)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^+ = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^- + \mathbf{K}_{k+1} [\mathbf{y}_{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\Gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^-)] \quad (22)$$

Let $\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- = \mathbf{x}_{k+1} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^-$ represent the priori state estimation errors and $\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+ = \mathbf{x}_{k+1} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^+$ indicate the posteriori state estimation errors of the system, respectively. Then, we can get

$$\mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- (\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^-)^T) \quad (23)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k+1}^+ = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+ (\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+)^T) \quad (24)$$

The standard EKF is of the following form:

1) **Initialization**

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}_0) \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_0 = \mathbf{E}[(\mathbf{x}_0 - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0)(\mathbf{x}_0 - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0)^T] \quad (26)$$

2) **State Prediction**

a) Calculation of Jacobian matrices

$$\mathbf{A}_k = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_k} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_k = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+} \quad (27)$$

b) Time update equation

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^- = \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1}^+) \quad (28)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_k^- = \mathbf{A}_{k-1} \mathbf{P}_{k-1}^+ \mathbf{A}_{k-1}^T + \mathbf{Q}_k \quad (29)$$

3) State Update

a) Computation of Jacobian matrices

$$\mathbf{C}_k = \left. \frac{\partial \Gamma(\mathbf{x}_k)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_k} \right|_{\mathbf{x}_k = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-} \quad (30)$$

b) Computation of the Kalman gain at time instant k

$$\mathbf{K}_k = \mathbf{P}_k^- \mathbf{C}_k^T \times (\mathbf{C}_k \mathbf{P}_k^- \mathbf{C}_k^T + \mathbf{R}_k)^{-1} \quad (31)$$

c) Update of the posterior state estimate at the time instant k

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+ = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^- + \mathbf{K}_k [\mathbf{y}_k - \Gamma(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-)] \quad (32)$$

d) Update of state estimation error covariance at the time instant k

$$\mathbf{P}_k^+ = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_k \mathbf{C}_k) \mathbf{P}_k^- \quad (33)$$

Remark 1: Due to the characteristics of simple calculation and high efficiency, the conventional extended Kalman filter has been widely utilized in many areas, such as dynamic state estimation of power system, vehicle state estimation, and state estimation of lithium battery [37]-[38]. The standard EKF method can work well if the measurement data acquired are correct. However, these assumptions are difficult to hold true, due to sensor data dropouts inevitably occur in the transmission channels of conventional measurements from the meters to the control center. The sensor data loss may degrade the performance of conventional EKF, which can severely distort its estimation results, result in unreliable state estimates.

B. Resilient Fault Tolerant Extended Kalman Filter

In this subsection, in order to acquire a more reliable and accurate estimation result of power grid synchronization, which could mitigate the adverse effect of inevitably partial sensor data loss, a resilient dynamic estimation method for smart power grid synchronization, named as resilient fault tolerant extended Kalman filter is developed.

Considering that partial measurements of the smart grid synchronization system in (17) are missing, if all the conditions in Eq. (34) are satisfied

$$\begin{cases} E[\mathbf{v}_k] = 0, E[\boldsymbol{\zeta}_k] = 0, E[\mathbf{v}_k \boldsymbol{\zeta}_k^T] = 0, \\ E[\mathbf{v}_k \mathbf{v}_k^T] = \mathbf{Q}_k, E[\boldsymbol{\zeta}_k \boldsymbol{\zeta}_k^T] = \mathbf{R}_k, \\ \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{k-j} = 1(k=j); \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{k-j} = 0(k \neq j) \\ E[\mathbf{v}_k \mathbf{x}_0^T] = 0, E[\boldsymbol{\zeta}_k \mathbf{x}_k^T] = 0 \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

then the RFTEKF method can be derived, which is for grid synchronization DSE with partial missing measurements.

Based on the DSE model of power grid synchronization described in (17), the RFTEKF method can be further constructed as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^- = \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+) \quad (35)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^+ = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^- + \mathbf{K}_{k+1} [\mathbf{y}_{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\Xi}_{k+1} \Gamma(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^-)] \quad (36)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Xi}$ is used to describe the partial missing measurements. To express convenience, we define $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_k \triangleq \mathbf{y}_k - \boldsymbol{\Xi}_k \Gamma(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-)$.

Then, the optimal filter gain of RFTEKF can be derived as follows

$$\mathbf{K}_{k+1} = \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- \mathbf{C}_{k+1}^T \bar{\boldsymbol{\Xi}}_{k+1} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{k+1}^{-1} \quad (37)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{k+1} = \bar{\boldsymbol{\Xi}}_{k+1} \otimes (\mathbf{C}_{k+1} \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- \mathbf{C}_{k+1}^T) + \mathbf{R}_{k+1}$ and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\Xi}}_{k+1} = E(\boldsymbol{\Xi}_{k+1})$.

And the \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^+ can be written as

$$\mathbf{P}_{k+1}^+ = \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- - \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{k+1} \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^T \quad (38)$$

Proof: Let

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+ = \mathbf{x}_{k+1} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^+ \\ \mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- = \mathbf{x}_{k+1} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^- \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

where \mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+ represents the state estimation error, \mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- indicates the prior state prediction error. According to Eq. (35), \mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+ and \mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- can be further rewritten as follows

$$\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+ = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k) + \mathbf{v}_k - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^- - \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{k+1} \quad (40)$$

$$\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k) + \mathbf{v}_k - \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+) \quad (41)$$

Taylor expansion is used to linearize $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k)$ and $\Gamma(\mathbf{x}_{k+1})$ at $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^-$, respectively, and leaving only the first order term

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+) + \mathbf{A}_k \mathbf{e}_k^+ \\ \mathbf{A}_k = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k)}{\partial \mathbf{x}_k} \right|_{\mathbf{x}_k = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+} \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

$$\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- = \mathbf{A}_k \mathbf{e}_k^+ + \mathbf{v}_k \quad (43)$$

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}) = \Gamma(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^-) + \mathbf{C}_{k+1} \mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- \\ \mathbf{C}_{k+1} = \left. \frac{\partial \Gamma(\mathbf{x}_{k+1})}{\partial \mathbf{x}_{k+1}} \right|_{\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}^-} \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

$$\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+ = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \bar{\boldsymbol{\Xi}}_{k+1} \mathbf{C}_{k+1}) \mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- - \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \boldsymbol{\zeta}_{k+1} \quad (45)$$

According to the Eq. (37), \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- can be computed by

$$\mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- = E[\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^- (\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^-)^T] = \mathbf{A}_k \mathbf{P}_k^+ \mathbf{A}_k^T + \mathbf{Q}_k \quad (46)$$

Due to $\mathbf{v}_k, \mathbf{e}_k, \boldsymbol{\zeta}_k$ and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\Xi}}_k$ are mutually uncorrelated, according to Eq. (39), \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^+ is generated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^+ &= E[\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+ (\mathbf{e}_{k+1}^+)^T] \\ &= \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- - \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- \mathbf{C}_{k+1}^T \bar{\boldsymbol{\Xi}}_{k+1} \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^T \\ &\quad - \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \bar{\boldsymbol{\Xi}}_{k+1} \mathbf{C}_{k+1} (\mathbf{P}_{k+1}^-)^T \\ &\quad + (\mathbf{K}_{k+1} - \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^*) \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{k+1} (\mathbf{K}_{k+1} - \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^*)^T \\ &\quad - \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^* \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{k+1} (\mathbf{K}_{k+1}^*)^T + \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^* \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{k+1} \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^{*T} \\ &\quad + \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{k+1} (\mathbf{K}_{k+1}^*)^T \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

when $\mathbf{K}_{k+1} = \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^* = \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- \mathbf{C}_{k+1}^T \bar{\Xi}_{k+1} \Lambda_{k+1}^{-1}$, \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^+ can acquire the minimum value. Thus, \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^+ and \mathbf{K}_{k+1} can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^+ = \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- - \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \Lambda_{k+1} \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^T \\ \mathbf{K}_{k+1} = \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- \mathbf{C}_{k+1}^T \bar{\Xi}_{k+1} \Lambda_{k+1}^{-1} \end{cases} \quad (48)$$

This completes the proof. \blacksquare

At last, for the sake of simplicity, Algorithm 1 is a brief summary of the proposed RFTEKF method.

Algorithm 1: Resilient Fault Extended Kalman Filter Method

- 1: **Step1**: set $k = 0$, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0, \mathbf{P}_0, T_s$;
 - 2: **Step2**: calculate $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-$ at time instant k by Eq. (35)
 - 3: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^- \leftarrow \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1}^+)$;
 - 4: **Step 3**: calculate \mathbf{P}_k^- at the time instant k by Eq. (46)
 - 5: $\mathbf{P}_k^- = \mathbf{A}_{k-1} \mathbf{P}_{k-1}^+ \mathbf{A}_{k-1}^T + \mathbf{Q}_k$;
 - 6: **Step 4**: update the gain matrix \mathbf{K}_k at the time instant k by Eq. (37)
 - 7: $\mathbf{K}_{k+1} = \mathbf{P}_{k+1}^- \mathbf{C}_{k+1}^T \bar{\Xi}_{k+1} \Lambda_{k+1}^{-1}$
 - 8: **Step 5**: update the estimated state vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+$ by Eq. (36)
 - 9: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+ = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^- + \mathbf{K}_k \left[\mathbf{y}_k - \bar{\Xi}_k \Gamma(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^-) \right]$;
 - 10: **Step 6**: update the estimation covariance matrix \mathbf{P}_k^+ by Eq. (38)
 - 11: $\mathbf{P}_k^+ = \mathbf{P}_k^- - \mathbf{K}_k \left[\bar{\Xi}_k \otimes (\mathbf{C}_k \mathbf{P}_k^- \mathbf{C}_k^T) + \mathbf{R}_k \right] \mathbf{K}_k^T$;
 - 12: **Step 7**: output the state estimation results of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k^+$, and update the time instant
 - 14: **Step 8**: $k = k + 1$, go back to **Step2**
 - 15: until $k = T_s$, end loop
-

Remark 2: When designing the estimator, literature [35] only adopted the statistical property of measurement data loss in formula (18) to improve the calculation accuracy. But when referring to the design and implementation of the estimator in [39], the time stamp technology in the sensor network can be used to know Ξ . In this literature, similar to [40], only Ξ statistical characteristic are used to construct the best possible filter gains for the RFTEKF. More importantly, by using one Riccati, the gains can be computed offline [39]. Meanwhile, the timestamp mechanism is used in the implementation of the RFTEKF approach to assume that Ξ is known online.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this section, to show the effectiveness and resistance of the proposed resilient fault tolerant extended Kalman filter against partial missing measurements, detailed numerical simulations are implemented in this section.

A. Test Systems

To verify the validity and robustness of the proposed method, numerical signal analysis, WECC 9-bus test and real power system with DPGS test are carried out. The following

are the precise settings for each testing system.

Case Study 1: The proposed RFTEKF method is compared with FTEKF and conventional extended Kalman filter for the numerical signal with partial missing measurement.

Case Study 2: To further illustrate the effectiveness of the developed RFTEKF method, the discussed approaches are tested on the three-phase voltage imbalance signal that acquired between the bus 8 and bus 9 of the standard WECC 9-bus test system.

Case Study 3: In order to verify the effectiveness of the proposed method in the large power system with high proportion of new energy access, a signal from the actual power system with DPGS penetration in Henan Province, China is considered and tested to further demonstrate the scalability and effectiveness of the method.

In order to accurately track dynamic features of smart grid, in this paper, time step for the simulation is set at 0.25 seconds. The sampling frequency is selected as 2400HZ. It's important to note that each of the discussed approaches are carried out in MATLAB R2020b on a PC with the Intel Core CPU i5-7200U, 2.5 GHz and 8 GB RAM.

In addition, in order to obtain more comprehensive and substantial results, and to make the statistical results clearer and easier to understand, the overall performance indicator E_x introduced in the revised manuscript to evaluate the performance of each discussed algorithm, where the 100 Monte Carlo simulations are conducted, which is defined as follows:

$$E_x = \frac{1}{N_{MC}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{MC}} \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^{N_T} (\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k - \mathbf{x}_k)^2 / N_T} \quad (49)$$

where $N_{MC} = 100$ is the number of Monte Carlo runs; N_T is the simulation time steps, k represents the time instant, \mathbf{x} denotes the magnitude and phase angle of positive sequence voltage, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$ and \mathbf{x}_k are the estimated value and the truth value of the state variable, respectively.

B. Case Study 1: Numerical Signal Test

In this part, the numerical simulation of the three-phase unbalanced voltage signal is carried out. The performance of traditional EKF, FTEKF and the proposed RFTEKF are tested. In the simulation studies, the initial value of the amplitude of the unbalanced voltage is set to $[1, 1.2, 0.8]^T$ and the initial value of the phase angle is selected as $[0^\circ, 120^\circ, 240^\circ]^T$.

Fig. 2. Measurement y_1 with and without partial missing.

In the simulation, the sampling frequency is 2400 Hz. The initial value of the error covariance of the EKF, FTEKF and RFTEKF is chosen as $10^{-6} I_{n \times n}$. The system noise covariance and measurement noise covariance matrices are set as $Q_0 = 10^{-6} I_{5 \times 5}$, $R_0 = 10^{-6} I_{2 \times 2}$, respectively.

Fig.2 and Fig.3 respectively show the complete measurement information of y_1 and y_2 with and without partial missing measurements. Based on which, we have compared traditional EKF, FTEKF and proposed RFTEKF three methods state estimation tests for power grid synchronization. The comparison results of the discussed approaches are presented in Figs. 4-8.

Fig. 3. Measurement y_2 with and without partial missing.

Fig. 4. Estimation results of state variable x_1 by different methods.

Fig. 5. Estimation results of state variable x_2 by different methods.

Fig. 6. Estimation results of state variable x_3 by different methods.

As a result of the experimental findings, it can be seen that

the proposed resilient fault tolerant extended Kalman filter approach can accurately estimate each state variables even with the partial missing measurements. FTEKF is second because it only takes into account the statistical properties of the lost information. While due to the severe nonlinearity caused by the partial missing measurement, the conventional extended Kalman filter significantly deviates from the true value and is unable to converge to the real values of the five state trajectories. In the case of sensor data loss, the conventional EKF method exhibits numerical instability because the EKF methodology uses first order linearization to update the estimation covariance matrix and the mean of state.

Fig. 7. Estimation results of state variable x_4 by different methods.

Fig. 8. Estimation results of state variable x_5 by different methods.

Additionally, Table I provides a summary of the performance indices of EKF, FTEKF and the proposed RFTEKF methods for power grid synchronization with partial missing measurements. It can be seen that compared to the traditional EKF method and FTEKF, the estimation error of

the new RFTEKF methodology is significantly lower. These experimental outcomes are consistent with those reflected in the Figs. 4-8, which further verify and confirm the proposed RFTEKF approach is more robust and resistant to measurements with partly missing data.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Metric	EKF	FTEKF	RFTEKF
E_{x_1}	0.0498	0.0111	0.0003
E_{x_2}	1.2820	0.0478	0.0050
E_{x_3}	0.3469	0.0096	0.0024
E_{x_4}	0.8864	0.0122	0.0043
E_{x_5}	0.2490	0.0088	0.0019

C. Case Study 2: WECC 9-Bus Test

In this scenario, the 3-machine and 9-bus system of Western Electric Power Coordinating Committee (WECC) is selected as the test system [31]. The unbalanced voltage signal is acquired between the bus 8 and the bus 9 of the test system. the measurement data with partial missing are displayed in Figs. 9-10. Three-phase unbalanced voltage's initial amplitude and phase angle are $[1, 1.11, 0.89]^T$ and $[0^\circ, 120.33^\circ, 240.32^\circ]^T$, respectively. In addition, $10^{-6} \mathbf{I}_{n \times n}$ is selected as the initial value of the error covariance of the EKF and RFTEKF. The system noise covariance matrix is $\mathbf{Q}_0 = 10^{-6} \mathbf{I}_{5 \times 5}$ and the measurement noise covariance matrix is $\mathbf{R}_0 = 10^{-6} \mathbf{I}_{5 \times 5}$.

Fig. 9. Measurement y_1 with and without partial missing.

Fig. 10. Measurement y_2 with and without partial missing.

The conventional EKF, FTEKF and the RFTEKF approaches are implemented for the dynamic state estimation of WECC synchronization. The estimation outcomes based on EKF, FTEKF and RFTEKF are contrasted with the actual values of state variables, which are displayed in Figs. 11-15.

According to the experimental findings shown in Figs. 11-15, the synchronization estimation of traditional EKF deviates from the true value seriously under this scenario, which reflects that the conventional EKF is susceptible to partial missing measurement. FTEKF performs better than EKF because the estimator is designed with measurement missing in mind. The developed RFTEKF method, in contrast, outperforms the traditional EKF method and FTEKF in tracking the dynamic of WECC system accurately even with the partial missing measurements. These results demonstrate the excellent performance and numerical stability of the proposed RFTEKF method in the case of the partial missing measurement.

Fig. 11. Estimation results of state variable x_1 by different methods.

Fig. 12. Estimation results of state variable x_2 by different methods.

In addition, to acquire a quantitative understanding of the performance comparison of each discussed approaches, Table II provides an overview of the estimation error index for the proposed RFTEKF, FTEKF and EKF methods for the WECC test. It is evident from the table that the proposed RFTEKF method can achieve much smaller root-mean-square error than the conventional EKF. These experimental findings concur with the Case Study 2, which shows that RFTEKF method is more resilient and robust deal with the partial missing measurements.

Fig. 13. Estimation results of state variable x_3 by different methods.

Fig. 14. Estimation results of state variable x_4 by different methods.

Fig. 15. Estimation results of state variable x_5 by different methods.

TABLE II

PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Metric	EKF	FTEKF	RFTEKF
E_{x_1}	0.4781	0.0820	0.0025
E_{x_2}	1.2071	0.0890	0.0050
E_{x_3}	0.5236	0.0066	0.0021
E_{x_4}	1.1847	0.0580	0.0041
E_{x_5}	0.2166	0.049	0.0018

Furthermore, the synchronous estimation experiments to track the phase angle and amplitude of dynamic positive sequence voltage in WECC test system by using the traditional EKF, FTEKF and the developed RFTEKF method are carried out. The comparison outcomes of the methods outlined are shown in Figs. 16 and 17.

As demonstrated by the experimental results displayed in Figs 16-17, the estimation results of traditional Kalman filter

largely deviates from the true value of the voltage in the presence of partial missing measurements. The tracking effect of FTEKF is better than that of EKF, because it takes into account the problem of missing measurements, but only uses statistical characteristics, so the tracking effect is slightly inferior to RFTEKF. By contrast, the proposed RFTEKF can accurately track the amplitude and phase angle of the positive sequence voltage even with the incomplete measurement information, displaying significantly improved performance over the conventional EKF method and FTEKF. In addition, the performance indicators of the three methods are provided in Table III, and it is obvious that the deviation of the proposed RFTEKF approach is much smaller. These numerical results are consistent with those reflected in Figs.16-17, which further confirms the proposed RFTEKF method is more robust and resilient in the case of partial missing measurements.

Fig. 16. Estimation result of positive sequence phase angle by different methods.

Fig. 17. Estimation result of positive sequence voltage magnitude by different methods.

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Metric	EKF	FTEKF	RFTEKF
$E_{\hat{\theta}_p}$	1.2819	0.0098	0.0010
$E_{\hat{V}_p}$	0.2949	0.0080	0.0002

D. Case Study 3: Real Power System With DPGS Test

In this scenario, a signal from the actual power system with DPGS penetration in Henan Province, China, is considered. Specifically, the three-phase voltage at the 35KV bus bar near the wind-driven generator connection point is utilized and tested. The sampling frequency is 10000HZ and the simulation time is 1s. In the process of application, the initial covariance of state error is set as $10^{-6} I_{n \times n}$, and the covariance of process noise and measurement noise is $Q_0 = 10^{-10} I_{5 \times 5}$, $R_0 = 10^{-10} I_{5 \times 5}$ respectively.

Fig. 18. Measurement y_1 with and without partial missing.

Fig.18 and Fig. 19 show measurement variables y_1 and y_2 with and without partial measurement missing information, respectively. Under the condition of partial measurement missing, we use three algorithms to estimate the power grid voltage data synchronously.

Fig. 19. Measurement y_2 with and without partial missing

In Figs. 20-21, the results of grid synchronization estimation using voltage data collected at the point of interconnection of a wind turbine are shown respectively. Only the tracking effect of voltage amplitude and phase angle are shown.

The experimental results show that the conventional EKF method deviates from the true value trajectory seriously, since it was not designed with effect of partial missing measurements. By contrast, the RFTEKF and FTEKF methods can obtain higher accuracy of state estimation. In addition, due to the proposed RFTEKF approach can use the time-stamp technology to obtain packet loss information, so the estimation error of RFTEKF is minimal, these estimation results are not only further confirm the strong robustness of the RFTEKF against partial missing measurements but also demonstrate its good scalability.

Fig. 20. Estimation result of positive sequence phase angle by different methods.

Fig. 21. Estimation result of positive sequence voltage magnitude by different methods.

E. Case Study 4: Evaluation of Computational Efficiency

In order to satisfy various real-time applications of energy management system (EMS), the estimation approach for smart grid synchronization needs to be computationally efficient. As a result, to determine whether the computation time of RFTEKF presented in this paper is lower than the PMU sampling rate, the entire running time of the conventional EKF, FTEKF and RFTEKF for the Case Study 1, Case Study 2 and Case Study 3 are calculated, and the results are displayed in Fig. 22. It can be seen from the calculation time that RFTEKF method has similar computational efficiency to FTEKF. Because of the complicated formula in the update stage, the operating time of RFTEKF is slightly longer than that of FTEKF. However, it is still lower than the sampling rate of the PMU. Therefore, the proposed RFTEKF method can satisfy the requirements for real-time tracking of smart grid synchronization estimation.

Fig. 22. Total execution time of each discussed approach for different test system.

V. CONCLUSION

Accurate voltage synchronization under bad data, fault and distorted voltages conditions is a critical concern for properly controlling electrical energy transfer between a distributed power generation system (DPGS) and the grid. In this article, the lost information is considered to be known online by using the time-stamp technique, and the gain is calculated by using its statistical characteristic to design and implement the estimator, which can effectively reduce the influence of partial loss of sensor data on the state accuracy. Experimental data manifest that the proposed RFTEKF algorithm is robust and reliable for synchronous dynamic estimation of smart grid for various test systems with partial missing measurements. In future studies, we will focus on the collection of measurement data, as well as the analysis of statistical characteristics of the data.

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